

Interview guide for the qualitative pilot study

Translated from the Danish pilot interview guide.

Introductory information

The introduction covers the purpose of the interview, the main focus of the conversation, and the practical conditions for participation. This includes information about voluntary participation, the participant's right to decline questions or withdraw, anonymity and confidentiality, the possible use of anonymized statements, audio recording and transcription, the expected duration of the interview, and the opportunity to ask questions before and during the interview.

Interview themes and possible questions

The guide was used flexibly as a semi-structured interview guide; not all questions necessarily had to be asked in the order shown.

Theme	Possible interview questions
Participants' use of nature and background understanding of nature connection	How often do you spend time in nature? What do you do there? Are you usually with someone or alone? Are you in nature as often as you would like? What does nature mean to you in everyday life? Do you feel connected to nature? Do you actively work with nature-related issues or know a lot about nature?
Attitudes toward using guidance in nature and toward using technology in nature	Have you tried other forms of nature guidance before? What did you think of them? What do you think about having an app as a guide in nature? Would other formats be preferable?
Whether nature experiences can be strengthened through nature stories	What happened when you sat at the stops? What did you experience while listening to the stories? What happened to your nature experience when you experienced nature through a story? Was there a difference in how you felt when you sat with and without the stories?

Theme	Possible interview questions
Whether the stories increased attention to nature	<p>In the instructions, you were guided to direct your attention toward different experiences. What happened when you did this?</p> <p>Did the stories increase or change your attention to the nature around you?</p> <p>Do you usually notice the nature around you?</p> <p>What do you particularly notice?</p> <p>Is there anything that can draw your attention away from the nature experience?</p>
Whether nature stories can increase motivation for nature visits	<p>Could you imagine listening to these stories here again?</p>
Whether the stories encourage individual or social activity	<p>Would you come back again with someone or alone?</p> <p>Would you listen to the stories together with someone, or use something from the stories, for example the information about the plants?</p>
Preferred content of nature stories	<p>If you were to review these stories, what positive or negative aspects would you highlight?</p> <p>What would you like to change?</p>
Target group	<p>Would you recommend the stories to others? Who would you recommend them to?</p>
Usability of the app	<p>How was the app to use?</p>
Accessibility	<p>How did you experience the accessibility of the route?</p>
Closing	<p>I have no further questions. Is there anything you would like to ask or add?</p>